

TOWARD A NEW FORMULATION OF SOLIPSISM

Abstract: The paper proposes a formal approach to ontological solipsism based on a system of quasi-equational axioms (S1–S5), where solipsism is defined as a relationship between **Ego** (I) and **Datum** (D), where existence (E) is their particular sum ($E = I + D$). The author constructs a mathematical space of solipsisms (SOLIP) as a set of pairs (I, D) and introduces a two-level ordering: between abstraction classes (according to the value of E) and within classes (lexicographically). The model is enhanced with the concept of the **Turing Subject** – a finite automaton (I) which interacts with an infinite tape (D), allowing self-awareness to be operationalised as recursion. As a result of interpreting a certain Hilbert’s axiom, a more comprehensive model of solipsism is formulated in the form of the **Solipsistic Subject**. This interdisciplinary approach integrates the elements of logic, computational theory, and ontology, offering novel tools for analysing solipsism as a formal system.

0. Introduction

The aim of the paper is to present the results of new analyses on the definitional formulation of solipsism (S.). The discussion will be limited to *ontological solipsism*, since we believe that other versions – such as epistemological, methodological, or ethical solipsism – are derivative of the ontological core. We assume that the definitional formulation of S. is a conceptual construct derived from basic terms relevant in the context.

In other words, the position known as ontological solipsism is inherently conceptual and must be expressed using concepts¹. Our empirical reference point is a set of sixteen formulations of solipsism compiled in Olszewski (2020)², which collectively reveal that

¹ We talk here about concepts, although we are not entirely sure if this is entirely appropriate. Instead of concepts, we could also speak of meanings or senses. At times, we will also make use of these terms.

² [S.1] (A. Heyting) S.:= the doctrine that assigns the Self a primary role. [S.2] (A. Heyting) S.:= “The entire world consists solely of my representations”. [S.3] (B. Russell) S.:= “The belief that I alone exist”; a. dogmatic: “there is nothing beyond data”; b. sceptic: “one cannot know anything beyond data”; c. drastic: “everything consists in the following (what I perceive and remember)”; d. less drastic: “I accept everything that is present in my spirit according both to pure reason and to orthodox psychology; hence also unconscious perceptions”. [S.4] (F.C.S. Schiller) S.:= “the doctrine that all existence is experience and that there is only one experiencer”. [S.5] (F.H. Bradley) “I cannot transcend experience, and experience must be my experience. From this it follows that nothing beyond my self exists; for what is experience is its [the self’s] states”. [S.6] (C. Brunet) “Everything exists only with the consciousness; I wish to say that there is a contradiction in attributing a positive existence to a thing of

conceptual formulations of this view primarily employ three concepts and their corresponding semantic categories of names³: *Existence*, *Ego*, and *Datum*, which we will denote respectively by the letters: E(xistence), I (Ego), D(atum). Accordingly, to articulate a solipsistic stance is to address, among others, the following foundational questions: What is Existence (Being)? What is the given (Datum)? To whom is it given? What is the relationship between that what is given and the one to whom it is given?

1. A new formulation of solipsism

We propose to define solipsism using the following theses expressed as quasi-equations⁴:

- (S1) $E = I + D$. (**Interpretation:** Existence (being) is the entanglement of Ego and Datum).
- (S2) $E - D = I$. (**Interpretation:** Ego is sufficient to establish the reality of Existence, even in the absence of external phenomena.)
- (S3) $D = 0$, when $I = 0$. (**Interpretation:** Existence depends entirely on Ego, and in its absence, there is no meaningful reality or we say that Datum collapses).⁵
- (S4) $I \neq D$, when $I \neq 0$. (**Interpretation:** This thesis states that non-empty Ego is necessarily distinct from Datum).⁶
- (S5) $E - I = 0$. (**Interpretation:** Though debatable, this thesis emphasises a specific interdependence between I and D).

Let us note that these formulations introduce an additional foundational concept – 0. It signifies the *emptiness* of a given concept, for example, $D = 0$ means that the Ego receives

which one does not think at all”. [S.7] (A. Pastore) “(...) l’identificazione di tutta la realtà, al mio io individuale, consciente e pensante, unica realtà”. [S.8] (P. Foulquié) “Le solipsiste dit: Il n’y a que moi”. [S.9] (R. Eisler) S.:= the view that “daß das eigene Ich allein, das Seiende ist, daß alles Sein im eigenen Ich, im eigenen Bewußtsein beschlossen ist”. [S.10] (S. Thornton) “I am the only mind which exists”, or “My mental states are the only mental states”. [S.11] (K. Popper) S.:= “is a theory that I, and only I, exist”. [S.12] (R. Watson) S.:= “the thesis that one can be conscious only of one’s own sensations and ideas in the present moment”. [S.13] (W. Todd) S.:= “Analytic solipsism is defined as the view which says that all the statements of ordinary language can be translated without loss of meaning into a language whose primitive terms refer only to the mental phenomena of the speaker”. [S.14] (Wikipedia) S.:= “Nur das eigene Ich existiert. Nichts außerhalb des eigenen Bewusstseins existiert, auch kein anderes Bewusstsein”. [S.15] (A. Schopenhauer) “Nach Schopenhauer kann der Solipsismus, der alle Erscheinungen außer dem eigenen Individuum für Phantome hält, als ernstliche Überzeugung »allein im Tollhause« gefunden werden”. [S.16] (A. Olszewski) S.:= only I and my Projection exist (Datum).

³ In Leśniewski’s terms.

⁴ In earlier works on solipsism (Olszewski 2020; 2024; 2025), I proposed slightly different equations to describe solipsism, such as (S3) $E - I = \text{nonE}$ or (S2) $I \neq D$. I am now also changing the numbering of the theses. Intuitive terms for the operation ‘+’ include ‘entanglement’, while ‘detachment’ seems more appropriate for the operation ‘-’.

⁵ To these theses, we could add thesis (S5) $E - I = 0$, which poses interpretative problems. Its meaning would be that E, deprived of the Ego, yields an empty Datum.

⁶ In other words, without the Ego, nothing else can have meaning (or existence).

empty data (i.e., no data). In semantic spaces relevant to our conceptual presentation of solipsism, the zero vector may symbolise the lack of context or of any semantic content. Since our terms belong to semantic categories of names⁷, a common belief arises: when we speak of the emptiness of a name, we mean the emptiness of its denotation (i.e., the set of its referents). However, here the situation is slightly different: alongside the emptiness of denotation, we have the absence of the content (meaning) of a name. We must also distinguish between non-being and the emptiness of a concept. To clarify what $I = 0$ means – and indirectly what $D = 0$ means – we will use an analogy from set theory and the concept of the empty set. Given a non-empty set X with n elements, we can successively remove its elements. When the last element is removed, the set does not disappear but becomes an empty set, which has no elements yet still exists, although its cardinality equals zero. Analogously, we can say the same of Ego and Datum: we say they are empty, though not non-existent. Let us observe that some names can have an empty denotation but still carry meaning (e.g., the largest prime number). The reverse also seems possible – when a name is semantically empty but has a non-empty denotation (e.g., someone names their pet ‘Bzwtgo’). Our formulation thus also establishes a subtle ontological relationship between I and D . Thesis S1 can be expressed as: existence is the entanglement of Ego and Datum, and Thesis S2 as: detaching D from E preserves Ego; whereas detaching Ego (S5) yields emptiness in such a way that the Datum ceases to have meaning. Similarly, thesis S4 equivalently says: if Ego has content, it is distinct from the content of Datum. For precision, let us also define the term *solipsist*: it denotes someone who endorses a solipsistic view. Ego entangled with Datum together constitute the *Solipsistic Subject* (SS).

2. The consistency of quasi-equations S1–S5

In recent years, the concept of vector space models (VSMs) has been dynamically developed. In these models, meaning – understood as the contextual use of words or phrases – is represented as vectors in a vector space and as matrices. VSMs are, at their core, a theory of meaning representation⁸. From a philosophical standpoint, such spaces offer a promising empirical approach to linguistic meaning, based on Wittgenstein’s notion of meaning as use. Furthermore, it is possible to represent the principles of **solipsism** using **vectors in a semantic**

⁷ In Leśniewski’s terms.

⁸ “In semantic vector space models, words or phrases are represented as vectors in a high-dimensional space, where the distance between two vectors reflects the semantic similarity between the corresponding words or phrases. These models are typically trained using unsupervised learning techniques, such as singular value decomposition (SVD) or word2vec, on large corpora of text data”. <https://ladal.edu.au/svm.html> [16.01.2025]

space, thus enabling philosophical ideas to be expressed through mathematical formalism. Vector spaces⁹ are essential to the representation of semantic relationships.

Using the concept of a trivial vector space (a Hilbert's space), we will demonstrate the consistency of the theses (S1)–(S5). Specifically:

FACT: The set of theses (S1)–(S5) is consistent.

Proof: Let us consider our model as the trivial vector space (the zero space) containing a single vector $[0]$. Thus, the universe of our model is $U = \{[0]\}$, and the vector algebra can be written as $(\{[0]\}; +)$, when this structure is an abelian group. For any valuation h of the variables in the theses (i.e., E, I, D) and the constant 0, $h(0) = [0]$; and for usual operations in a vector space: vector addition (+), subtraction (−), and scalar multiplication with real numbers. There exists only one h with the properties: $h(E) = h(I) = h(D) = h(0) = [0]$. We verify our formulas under this valuation: $h(E = I + D) = ([0] = [0] + [0])$; $h(E - D = I) = ([0] - [0] = [0])$. The implication: $h(I) = [0] \Rightarrow h(D) = [0]$ holds since the consequent is true. The implication $h(I) \neq 0 \Rightarrow h(I) \neq h(D)$ is also true, as its antecedent is false. These statements obtained through the mapping of h , are theorems of the zero space, which indicates that they simultaneously hold within the model – and this completes the proof.

This model demonstrates, first, that a model in vector spaces is simultaneously a representation of the subject's world of content or meanings. Second, it shows that the only element of the model is the zero vector $[0]$, which intuitively corresponds to **empty meaning** in semantic spaces, as it contains no semantic content, yet formally exists as an element of space. This means that in this model, Existence (E), Ego (I), and Datum (D) all lack semantic content. This constitutes the most minimal possible model of a semantic space – one devoid of any differentiation in meaning. The absence of semantic content may be interpreted as a case of radical solipsism. However, the formal structure of a vector space enables operations on these 'empty' elements in accordance with the axioms of the theory. Let us note that the theory composed of theses (S1)–(S5) implies certain properties, which is unsurprising, as these theses function as axioms. If '+' and '−' are interpreted as vectors in a vector space, the theses imply the uniqueness of Ego for given D and E: if we have $E = I_1 + D$ and $I_2 + D = E$, then $I_1 = E - D$

⁹ Cf. (Turney, Pantel 2010). With the help of AI, I conducted some analyses (not described here) on terms that define solipsism using vector spaces and the BERT model. The results highlight the complexity of solipsism both as a philosophical conception and as a semantic construct, which opens up promising avenues for further interdisciplinary studies.

$= I_2$. Similarly, for given E and I : if $E = I + D_1$ and $E = I + D_2$, then $D_1 = D_2$. These properties may not hold in extended interpretations of the subject, and – as we will show below – they break down in the case of the Turing Subject. In the interpretation involving the Turing Subject (below), it is established – based on relevant theorems – that replacing the Ego of this subject (a DFA, i.e., deterministic finite automaton) with more powerful automata, such as a nondeterministic finite automaton (NFA), a pushdown automaton (PDA), or a probabilistic finite automaton (PFA), does not increase the computational power of the machine but only its efficiency. The same applies to the Datum in this interpretation, represented by the tape. Machines equipped with multiple tapes or multi-dimensional tapes, etc., also do not enhance the computational power of the machine – that is, the subject – but only its operational efficiency¹⁰. We can summarise these observations more succinctly by adopting the following formulation: the model of solipsism presented in the next section, in the form of the Turing Subject (TS), is defined as an ordered pair: $TS = S_n = (I_n, D_n)$, for some fixed n , where I_n is DFA, and D_n is an infinite tape. Using this formulation of solipsism, we can more clearly express the different variants of TS. For example, consider a TS where: $S_{TS} = (I_{PDA}, D(\text{Tape}))$. According to formal results cited by Odifreddi (1989: 5), the following holds: $I_{PDA} + D(\text{Tape}) = E = I_{DFA} + D(\text{Tape})$, where PDA refers to a pushdown automaton, and DFA to a deterministic finite automaton. This equality shows that even when the Ego or Datum of TS is enriched in certain ways, the computational power of the Turing Subject remains the same.

3. An alternative model of solipsism: the Turing Subject

Alan Turing developed the conception of a computing machine, now known in his honour as the Turing machine. He also demonstrated the existence of a universal Turing machine (UTM), which, in our framework, can be interpreted as a model of the subject. We shall refer to it as the Turing Subject (TS). Our aim is to align this model with the structure outlined by Hilbert's Axiom (HA) and the Solipsistic Subject (SS). The universal Turing machine (UTM) consists of two components: a finite automaton (DFA) and an infinite tape (Tape)¹¹.

(AT1) The finite automaton (with a finite number of states and a finite alphabet; DFA) thinks, in the sense that it executes a given finite program¹².

¹⁰ For a synthetic summary of the results on this issue, see (Odifreddi 1989: 50).

¹¹ Our considerations are highly simplified, but this does not affect the validity of the conclusions. For precise definitions, such as DFA, see, e.g., (Sipser 2006: 35).

¹² It can be said that the program 'physically' resides on the tape, which serves as memory.

(AT2) The finite automaton operates on a tape that is (potentially) infinite (T).

(AT3) The finite automaton, in conjunction with data on the tape, can:

- a. erase and write symbols;
- b. read and recognise previously learned symbols;
- c. move left, right, or stay in place;
- d. change its internal state;
- e. halt computation.

(AT4) The UTM possesses a form of quasi-self-reflection, as guaranteed by the recursion theorem (I).

Using the terminology developed in earlier sections, we can express the UTM as: UTM = DFA + T. The infinite tape can be understood either as actually infinite or potentially infinite, in accordance with Aristotle's distinction between types of infinity. Either infinity suffices to serve as a kind of memory, capable of recording and storing an arbitrarily large but finite amount of data. It is worth emphasising that the reader within the Turing machine is itself a finite automaton, while the machine as a whole (i.e., a reader and a tape) exceeds the computational power of a finite automaton due to the presence of (potentially) infinite tape, which allows more complex computations to be simulated. The Turing Subject (TS) can thus be seen as a *part* – in a specific, structured sense – of the Solipsistic Subject (SS). The SS equips the Turing Subject with memory, the role of which is fulfilled by the (potentially) infinite tape, i.e., Datum. This can also be expressed by referring to the diagram representing the structure of the Turing Subject (TS), which is derived from the schema of the Hilbert Subject¹³. However, the empirical realisation of TS – a physical computer – is not a Turing machine in the strict sense, as it lacks access to a tape which is even potentially infinite. Similarly, a human being, understood as an *empirical subject* (i.e., a concrete specimen of the species *Homo sapiens*), does not possess access to a tape even potentially infinite. We call the idealised version of an *empirical subject* the *transcendental subject*, following Kant's terminology – and this is what we here refer to as the *Solipsistic Subject* (SS)¹⁴.

Let us now briefly discuss, by way of a digression, the notion of *self-reflection* as present in axioms of subjects (SS5) and (AT4). In computability theory, this function is grounded in Kleene's recursion theorem, which is valid for Turing machines. The theorem can be stated as follows: for any total computable function f , there exists a number e such that $\phi_e = \phi_{f(e)}$, where

¹³ The relationship between the Turing Subject and the Hilbert Subject is discussed in (Brożek, Olszewski 2013).

¹⁴ Cf. (Olszewski 2009). The relationship between the Turing Subject and the Hilbert Subject is discussed in (Brożek, Olszewski 2013).

ϕ_e is the computable function with index e , f_i is a total function, and $f(e)$ is itself the index of a computable function. The program below demonstrates the idea of self-reference: fp function is the identity function ($f(x) = x$), which is obtained by using a fixed-point construction. It uses a lambda function to obtain a minimal form¹⁵:

```
fp = (lambda f: f(f))(lambda x: x)

print(fp(42))      # 42

print(fp("Hello")) # Hello
```

It is relatively easy to notice that the TS is, in essence, a solipsist, as it satisfies the five principles (S1)–(S5). This property will be utilised in the remainder of the work. TS is a combination of a DFA and an infinite tape; when the tape is detached from TS, what remains is the DFA alone. If there is no reader (DFA), then no computation can occur on the tape, and the tape is semantically empty. Conversely, if the DFA is active in any way, it becomes distinguishable from the tape. A key feature of TS is that it satisfies S5, since $TS - DFA = 0$, i.e., when a machine is deprived of its reader, it no longer carries any meaning and becomes inactive.

4. The concept of the solipsistic subject

Building on the previous formulations of solipsism and referencing our earlier analysis¹⁶ of Hilbert's concept of the subject (HA), we now reformulate these ideas to develop a model of the *solipsistic subject* (SS)¹⁷. What follows is an instantiation of Hilbert's Axiom (HA), interpreted in a way that is more suitable for articulating the solipsistic subject (SS). For this subject, the following identity holds: $SS = \text{Ego} + \text{Datum}$:

(PS1) I Think¹⁸.

(PS2) I Think about Data (or: I Think Data) by using Concepts¹⁹.

¹⁵ An interesting fact is that this code comes from AI (ChatGPT).

¹⁶ Cf. (Brożek, Olszewski 2013).

¹⁷ The following formulation is more faithful to Hilbert's axiom, though further removed from our applications: **PS1**: I have the ability to think things. **PS2**: I can designate these things with simple symbols (e.g., a, b, X, Y) in a perfectly characteristic way. **PS3**: I can always unambiguously recognise these symbolised things again. **PS4**: My thought operates with these symbolised things according to definite laws. **PS5**: Through introspection (self-observation), I am able to know and completely describe these laws governing my thought processes.

¹⁸ Thinking is generally understood to include reasoning according to the rules of logic and the use of concepts.

¹⁹ I do not think any Data means *I do not think*. Cf. (Veronese 1981: footnote 2). We must say: I do not think any Data and I do not think concepts means *I do not think*. At least that is how it seems. Theoretically, it might be as Veronese claims, but an argument would be needed to support his position. Hilbert said: I think about things (and I think things). Cf. (Brożek, Olszewski 2014).

(PS3) I Can:

- (a) create, analyse, and understand Concepts;
- (b) label freely some Concepts or Data with other Data (my-Data, symbols)²⁰;
- (b) re-use my-Data (symbols).

(PS4) My thoughts operate with my-Data (and Concepts) according to definite laws which I can completely describe.

(PS5) I have a capacity for self-reflection²¹.

Def. I: Datum = the whole of Data²².

Hilbert treated his conception of the subject as a kind of an axiom, though, to the best of our knowledge, he never used it to construct a theory²³. Arguably, this axiom is not entirely original to Hilbert, but was at least partially inspired by G. Veronese, who, in his work (Veronese 1891: 1–2), introduced many different principles, including similar axioms and definitions²⁴.

In our view, this reformulated axiom describes the *Solipsistic Subject* (SS), and its relevance lies primarily in the domain of ontology. To demonstrate the deductive power of this axiom, we derive Descartes' famous thesis²⁵ – *Cogito, ergo sum* – using a law from first-order predicate logic with identity, which H. Scholz referred to as Descartes's generalised fundamental theorem. Its formal structure is as follows:

[T1] $A(x) \equiv \exists_{y=x} A(y)$.²⁶

²⁰ My-Data are data chosen and established by me.

²¹ It appears that an open question is whether the Ego knows itself directly or through the mediation of the Datum.

²² Data are *impressions, ideas, or mental representation*. Concepts are and belong to my mind or the "I".

²³ Hilbert's Axiom comes from a lecture he gave, recorded in the form of notes by attendees in 1905. Strictly speaking, Hilbert referred to it as the 'axiom of thought' or the 'axiom of the existence of intelligence'. Cf. (Hallet 1994) and (Brożek, Olszewski 2013: 403–404).

²⁴ (V1) I think. (V2) I think one thing or more things. (V3) I think one thing first, and then another thing. (V5) One or more things or concepts are to be denoted by symbols, e.g., the alphabet letter. **Def. I:** What in the thought corresponds to a thing is called an idea, a concept or a mental representation of the thing. **Def. II:** If I think one thing then it is said this thing is given or posited through thinking; when I think a thing, it is said to be given to the thought. **Def. III:** When *first* many things, e.g. A,B,C,D, are given or posited, and *later* I think about A,B,C it is said: I *abstract or detach the thing D or subtract D from the given* things, i.e. A,B,C, which are called the remaining things. **Def. IV:** To think *all* given things or any *single* thing is not to abstract from any of them. Por. (Veronese 1891:1-2).

²⁵ This thesis by Descartes can be understood in different ways from a logical perspective—either as an argumentative statement or as a conditional clause. We interpret it in the latter way, meaning that the thesis does not assert anything about real existence but merely establishes a conditional relationship between statements.

²⁶ Or equivalently: $A(x) \equiv \exists y ((y = x) \wedge A(y))$. (Rojek 2003) considers the problem linked to the fact that the method of introducing names in classical logic includes an assumption about the existence of the name's referent. The solution to this problem is to adopt Leśniewski's system of ontology. However, this issue does not affect our considerations. This formula is not a thesis of either free logic or, even more so, inclusive logic. On the other hand, the following is a thesis of free logic: $E!x \rightarrow (Px \equiv \exists y (y = x \wedge Py))$. The following counterexample shows that in free logic—where the referents of terms do not necessarily exist—it is not the case that "Pegasus is a winged horse" is equivalent to "Pegasus is identical with an existent winged horse."

From this, we can derive the thesis:

$$[T2] \quad A(x) \rightarrow \exists y(y = x).$$

Let us now assume that: I think.(SS1)

1. There exists some x such that x is identical with me and x thinks (from 1. and T1).
2. There exists some x such that x is identical with me (from 2., the distribution of the existential quantifier).
3. Therefore: I exist.(from 3.)²⁷.

Thus, by using first-order logic with identity, various conclusions can be derived from HA.

An important point for understanding all this the acknowledgement that the term “I”, as it appears in the formulation of the axiom, is ambiguous in the context under discussion. On the one hand, “I” refers to the central core of the subject, the governing point – what we might call point X – such as the transcendental I in the philosophies of Kant and Husserl. On the other hand, “I” can be understood more broadly as the entire system that includes concepts and reasoning, that is, the Cartesian mind or rational intellect. What is especially worth emphasising here is that within such a conception of the “I”, there are concepts that do not belong to Datum. Finally, the term “I” may also be understood as referring to the entire Solipsistic Subject (SS). The “I” as used in the formulation of SS includes both of the above meanings, but in our specific formulation of solipsism, we adopt the second meaning of “I”, namely as Ego. It should also be noted that such Ego perceives the Datum directly, while it perceives itself only indirectly, through the mediation of the Datum (at least in part).

5. Remarks on the ordering of solipsisms

In this section, we draw conclusions from the analyses in previous sections. Let us return to the idea that solipsism can be represented as an ordered pair of the form $S_n = (I_n, D_n)$, where S_n denotes the n -th solipsism, I_n and D_n are its Ego and Datum, respectively – each satisfying the quasi-equations (S1)–(S5). From the fact proven in Section 2, we know that the minimal solipsism is $S_0 = ([0], [0])$, in which both Ego and Datum are empty. If we have a given S_n , then using thesis S1, we can unambiguously determine $E_n = I_n + D_n$. For $n = 0$, $E_0 = [0] + [0] = [0]$. However, the converse does not hold: if E_n is given, it does not uniquely determine a solipsism S_n , as $I_n + D_n = E_n$ does not necessarily hold. Theoretically, E_n can be equated with the

²⁷ (Scholz 1931) and (Stupecki, Borkowski 1966: 111).

entanglement of a different pair I_m and D_k (i.e., $E_n = I_m + D_k$) providing that if $E_n = I_n + D_n$, where $n \neq k$, $n \neq m$. We must allow for this possibility, as we considered a similar case in Section 2 while discussing TS. Now, from an intuitive standpoint, it seems plausible that there exists a maximal solipsism within the class of all solipsisms: $S_{\max} = (I_{\max}, D_{\max})$, where $I_{\max} := \text{Deus (Absolute)}$, and $D_{\max} := \text{Universe}$ ²⁸. How, then, can solipsisms be ordered? We define the set of all solipsisms as $\text{SOLIP} := \{S_n: S_n = (I_n, D_n)\}$. In earlier works, it was done assuming that $S_n \leq S_m$ iff $I_n \subseteq I_m$, which holds when anything I_n can do, can also be done by I_m . However, this ordering fails to take into account relevant Datums that accompany Ego, which – when altered – yield different E. Moreover, the order defined on the set of Egos is only partial, as is the order on the set of Datums. As established earlier, both sets contain maximal elements with respect to their ordering relationships. Therefore, we now introduce a new order, more suitable for our purposes²⁹. First, on a class of solipsisms, we define an equivalence relationship \approx in the form $S_n \approx S_m$ iff $I_n + D_m = E_n = E_m = I_m + D_m$ and we will obtain $\text{SOLIP}_{\approx} = \{[S_n]_{\approx}: S_n = (I_n, D_n)\}$. Next, we say that the abstraction class determined by solipsism $[S_n]_{\approx}$ precedes the abstraction class determined by solipsism $[S_m]_{\approx}$ ($[S_n]_{\approx} \leq [S_m]_{\approx}$) iff: $E_n \leq_E E_m$, where solipsisms are ordered according to the principle of ascending being – meaning that if something exists in E_n , then it also exists in E_m . Within the abstraction classes $\text{SOLIP}_{\approx} = \{[S_n]_{\approx}: S_n = (I_n, D_n)\}$, we order solipsisms that share the same value $E_n = I_k + D_j$, following a lexicographic order $[S_n]_{\approx}$, i.e., if $E_n = I_k + D_j = I_n + D_m$, then $(I_k, D_j) \leq_S (I_n, D_m)$ iff $(I_k \leq_I I_n \wedge I_k \neq I_n) \vee (I_k = I_n \wedge D_j \subset D_m)$, i.e., if something exists in E_n , then it also exists in E_m . This order depends on the previously defined (partial) orders on the sets of Egos and Datums. As a result, the entire order on the SOLIP class is itself a partial order. This structure is by no means trivial, mainly because we lack precise formal definitions and must rely on intuition. Furthermore, the mathematical formulation of the problem is far from simple. As a conclusion, we can say that we are dealing with a form of hierarchy of being E_n . To summarise: the proposed two-level ordering on the set of solipsisms: $\text{SOLIP} := \{S_n: S_n = (I_n, D_n)\}$ establishes a linear order among classes of abstraction, while partially ordering the solipsisms within each class. As a result, the overall structure is a partial order that precisely captures the relationships between the components of solipsisms, though it does not form a lattice. In the context of solipsism theory, this ordering is significant because it

²⁸ I call this version of solipsism *Solideism*. Its elaboration can be found in (Olszewski 2024).

²⁹ In this part of the discussion, the relevant orders are denoted by the symbol \leq with a subscript indicating the set on which the given order is defined, e.g., \leq_I denotes an order on the set of Egos, that is, the set of Is.

highlights a fundamental hierarchy of being, and, in doing so, affirms that Ego takes precedence over Datum. Ontological solipsism is, in its essence, a statement about existence³⁰.

6. Conclusions

This paper proposes a new characterisation of solipsism through a system of quasi-equations, whose consistency is demonstrated using a model based on a trivial (zero) vector space. The very possibility of such a formalisation constitutes a non-trivial result. The vector space model is highly minimal. In the search for alternative models, the Turing Subject and the Hilbert Subject are introduced as structures that – though only in an intuitive sense – satisfy the formal conditions defined by the quasi-equations. Descartes’s principle *Cogito, ergo sum* is formally derived from the Hilbert Subject. The paper also offers a preliminary attempt to establish an ordering over the class of solipsisms. Rather than concluding the inquiry into solipsism, this work aims to initiate a broader theoretical investigation into this topic.

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³⁰ Of course, it is possible to approach this issue differently, which is why I treat my presentation more as a proposal for further elaboration rather than a final resolution.

